

The Sanctuary of Demeter and Kore at Eleusis

Secondary source

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**Secondary Source entry, prepared from a literature review by a Ph.D. RA*

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Roughly 14 km NW of the city centre of Athens lies the site of Eleusis. Although now an industrial suburb of Athens, for much of Antiquity, the ancient site was home to very important a sanctuary of Demeter and Kore, which was the centre of one of the most important ancient Mystery Cults--the Eleusinian Mysteries.

Date Range: 1480 BCE - 394 CE

Region: Sanctuary of Demeter and Kore at Eleusis

Region tags: Europe, Southeastern Europe, Southern Europe, Eastern Mediterranean, Greece, Aegean, Balkans, Attica

The archaeological site of the sanctuary of Demeter and Kore at Eleusis.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Cosmopoulos, M. 2015. *Bronze Age Eleusis and the Origins of the Eleusinian Mysteries*. Cambridge.

– Source 2: Binder, J. 1998. "The early history of the Demeter and Kore sanctuary at Eleusis." In R. Hägg (ed.), *Ancient Greek Cult Practice from the Archaeological Evidence. Proceedings of the Fourth International Seminar on Ancient Greek Cult, organised by the Swedish Institute at Athens, 22-24 October 1993* (pp. 131-139). Stockholm: Swedish Institute at Athens.

– Source 3: Clinton, K. 1993. "The Sanctuary of Demeter and Kore at Eleusis." In N. Marinatos, & R. Hägg (eds.), *Greek Sanctuaries. New Approaches* (pp. 110-124). London: Routledge.

Notes: Clinton, K. 1974. "The Sacred Officials of the Eleusinian Mysteries." *Transactions of the American Philosophical Society* 64.3: 1-143. Cosmopoulos, M. 2014. "The Sanctuary of Demeter at Eleusis." *The Bronze Age*. Athens: Βιβλιοθήκη τῆς ἐν Αθήναις Ἀρχαιολογικῆς Ἑταιρείας, 295-296. Kourouniotes, K., & Mylonas, G. (1933). "Excavations at Eleusis, 1932." *American Journal of Archaeology*, 37, 271-286. Kourouniotes, K., & Travlos, I. 1933-1935. "Τελεστήριον καὶ Ναός Δήμητρος." *Αρχαιολογικόν Δελτίον*, 15, 54-114. Kourouniotes, K., & Travlos, I. 1935-1936. "Συμβολή εἰς τὴν οἰκοδομικὴν ἱστορίαν τοῦ

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Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

↳ Type of excavation:

– Scientific

↳ Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1812, 1882-1997

↳ Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Eleusis

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

↳ Type of elevation

– Hill

Notes: The low Eleusinian Hill rises to the north of the site. It is a limestone formation that has been quarried since the Mycenaean period.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Type of feature

- Leveling of ground
- Terracing
- Clearing
- Trackway or road-surface
- Water feature
- Plantings

Notes: Quarrying of the Eleusinian Hill (on the north end of the site) has been continuous since Antiquity, as has cultivation of the Thriassion Plain for agriculture. Continuous modifications to the topography were made throughout Antiquity.

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

Notes: Eleusis was located within the demos of Eleusis, which was synoecised by Attica (by Theseus in Attic mythology).

Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– Yes

Notes: The temenos

Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Notes: The sanctuary of Demeter and Kore at Eleusis was located within the bounds of the town of Eleusis and the settlement surrounded the sanctuary.

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Notes: The town of Eleusis itself was an agricultural town which relied on the agriculture of the Thriasian plain but the sanctuary itself was located within the town.

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

Notes: The sanctuary's structures were continuously built throughout Antiquity.

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

Notes: The structures make up the sanctuary.

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Sacrificial

– Social

– Memorial

– Political

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

Notes: The site was already used as a sanctuary throughout most of Antiquity, certainly starting from 600 BC (Archaic period) during which period the site underwent intensive architectural activity. A terrace was constructed to support an Archaic temple

(rectangular) of Demeter as well as corresponding altars. In the Late Archaic period, the temple is replaced by the Peisistratid Telesterion, a large square structure supported by interior columns and fronted by a portico and three entrances. The sanctuary and the city of Eleusis are enclosed by a peribolos with at least 7 towers. The Kallichoron Well and the Ploutoneion (small temple to Hades in front of a cave) and many other structures were built during this phase. During the Classical period, Kimon begins a building program for the sanctuary after the Persian destructions, including a rebuilding of the sanctuary and the city's fortifications, a rebuilding of the Telesterion. Pericles continues the building program but to a larger scale. The Hellenistic period saw a decrease in building activity but a Bouleuterion and a stadium have been identified for this period. After the destruction of the sanctuary in AD 170 by Costoboci, architectural activity focused on rebuilding the destroyed features. The most significant period of construction at the sanctuary was during the reign of Hadrian, who started the construction of the Greater Propylaea, a large court in front of the sanctuary, two triumphal arches, a temple to Artemis and Poseidon, several altars and shrines, stoas, etc. This Imperial interest in Eleusis continues under the Antonines who expand the Telesterion.

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Burned

Notes: The sanctuary was destroyed several times: during the Persian Wars (480 BC), the invasion of the Costoboci (AD 170), and the Visigoths (AD 395). The sanctuary was rebuilt after the first two destructions but it never recovered from the Visigothic sack. The sanctuary continued to be in use until the early 5th c. AD when paganism was outlawed.

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

–As the result of war

–As the result of pillage

Notes: All three times.

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

↳ In antiquity

– More than once

↳ In modernity

– Post-Renaissance

Notes: It was no rebuilt but the site has been excavated and its ruins displayed in the last 200 years.

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Demeter and Kore (Persephone), as well as other subsidiary deities.

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– Yes

Notes: The excavators have identified numerous heroa (sg. heroon) throughout the site, based on literary sources. The Homeric Hymn to Demeter (as well as Pausanias and Plutarch) mention several figures (e.g. Triptolemos) who were worshipped as heroes at Eleusis.

Is it a cenotaph:

– No

Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

Specify

– King or emperor

– Private individual

– Other [specify]: Various aristocratic families of Athens (e.g. Peisistratids), the polis of Athens under the building programs of several politicians (Kimon, Pericles), Roman Emperors (esp. under Hadrian and the Antonines)

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– No

Notes: Many different groups of people and systems of labour contributed to the building of the sanctuary over centuries.

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Revealed by other kind of supernatural being(s) [specify]: Eleusis formed the central setting of the Homeric Hymn to Demeter, which recounted the abduction of Demeter's daughter Persephone and was the foundation myth of the sanctuary of Eleusis and the Eleusinian Mysteries.

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Yes

↳ Specify

– God(s) requested to be brought here

Notes: In the Homeric Hymn to Demeter, during Demeter's stay with Keleus and Metaneira (king and queen of Eleusis), Metaneira interrupted Demeter's attempt to immortalize Metaneira's infant son Demophon, and as penance Demeter ordered the people of Eleusis to build her a temple.

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– No

Notes: During the site's initial creation as a sanctuary, the motivation seems to have been largely local but external patrons (e.g. Roman emperors, and the city of Athens if we consider the Athenians an external sponsor) were instrumental in the various rebuildings of the sanctuary.

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expectation of favor in return

Notes: Divine command in its foundation myth, but also because the Eleusinian cult was said to bestow blessings on its initiates.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Notes: The Eleusinian cult was a mystery cult, which involved housing hiera (sacred objects). Because it was a mystery cult, these hiera are unknown but they did not seem to be sacred texts.

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Notes: The Ploutoneion is attached to a cave.

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– Percentage: 80

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– Square meters: 51

Notes: Kevin Clinton considers the Periclean phase of the Telesterion to be the largest public building in 5th c. BC Attica.

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– I don't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Quarried stone for the most part, some local, some imported.

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

- ↳ Are there gods depicted:
 - Yes
- ↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:
 - Yes
- ↳ Are there humans depicted:
 - Yes
- ↳ Are there animals depicted:
 - Yes
- ↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:
 - No
- ↳ Is the decoration non-figural:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Is it geometric/abstract
 - No
 - ↳ Floral motifs
 - Yes
 - ↳ Is it writing/caligraphy
 - Yes
 - Notes: If dedicatory inscriptions are counted as decoration.
 - ↳ Other [Specify]
 - Other [specify]: NA
- ↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can the decoration be revealed:
 - Yes

Notes: Depends on where it is in the sanctuary as there are parts of the sanctuary that can only be viewed by initiates.

– No

Notes: Depends on where it is in the sanctuary as there are parts of the sanctuary that can only be viewed by initiates.

↳ Are there statues present:

– Yes

↳ Cult statues:

– Yes

↳ Statues of gods/supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Statues of humans:

– Yes

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

Notes: Most sculptures would have been painted.

- ↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:
 - No
- ↳ Are they wall paintings:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:
 - Yes
- ↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:
 - Yes
- ↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:
 - Yes

↳ Are there mosaics present:

- No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

- Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

- Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

- Yes

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

- Yes

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

- Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: The same grouping of gods present in the Homeric Hymn to Demeter tend to be depicted in Eleusinian sculpture (Demeter, Persephone, Gaia, Hekate, Hermes, etc.)

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

Notes: Symbols of the Eleusinian cult, such as wheat sheaves, rosettes, torches, poppyseed heads, myrtle leaves, kernoi, kistai (tall baskets), were omnipresent at the sanctuary.

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Yes

↳ Human narratives

– Yes

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Notes: Eleusis had necropoleis but they were outside of the sanctuary in the time periods in discussion.

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– Yes

Notes: If we count the heroes worshipped at this site.

Human spirits can be seen:

– Field doesn't know

Human spirits can be physically felt:

– Field doesn't know

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: The Oceanid nymph Daeira was worshipped as a subsidiary deity at Eleusis. Daeira had her own priest at Eleusis called the daeirites.

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– Field doesn't know

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine spirits can be seen:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Mixed human-divine spirits can be physically felt:

– Field doesn't know

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– Yes

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal sacrifices:

– Yes [specify]: Pigs, bulls

↳ Are there human sacrifices:

– No

↳ Are the sacrificed humans associated in some way:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– No

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– Yes

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

Notes: IG II2 1672 consists of an account of the sanctuary's finances from the year 329/328 BC. The total cost of maintaining the sanctuary was 40,000 drachmas for that year. It also lists the various personnel employed by the sanctuary.

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Yes

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Yes

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– optional (common)

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– No

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

– No

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):

– Yes

Notes: The Hiera Odos/Via Sacra leading from Athens to Eleusis still exists today as a major road.

↳ Are these routes maintained together with the place:

– Yes

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that built/maintains the place:

– Yes

↳ Priests

– Yes

↳ Local elites

– Yes

↳ Private contributions

– Yes

↳ Does feasting occur in a specific location within the place:

– Yes [specify]: Various locations in the sanctuary, such as an L-shaped stoa building, may have been possible locations for dining.

Are festivals present:

– Yes

↳ Frequency of festivals

– specify: Two annual festivals (Lesser Mysteries and the Greater Mysteries), but also other annual festivals such as the Haloa.

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

- Only initiates
- Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Parts of the festivals were open to all Greek-speakers who were free from blood-guilt while other parts were restricted to the initiated.

↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

– Yes

↳ Requires special maintenance/cleansing of the place:

– Yes

↳ Requires new construction/decoration of the place:

– Yes

↳ Requires maintenance/replacement of cult statue(s):

– Field doesn't know

↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:

– number: Thousands

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):

– Yes

↳ Is food consumption limited to certain members of the population:

- Elites
- Non-elites
- Religious professionals

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: Tens of thousands

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: Small-scale rituals occurred perennially but large-scale rituals took place during designated festivals.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Yes

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– Yes

Notes: In addition to wine, it has been suggested that kykeon (a drink made of barley, a liquid, and an herb), which was drunk during the Mysteries, served as a psychedelic. At a Sanctuary to Demeter and Kore in Mas Castellar in Spain, traces of ergot (a fungus with psychedelic properties) were found in a vase and in the dental calculus of a young man, which could indicate that kykeon was being used to get high at Eleusis.

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– Yes

Notes: IG II2 1672 mentions "misthotoi" (paid employees) and how much they were paid at the sanctuary.

↳ Present part time

– Yes

Notes: Some personnel were based in Athens, which administered the sanctuary at Eleusis. For example, the Archon Basileus who oversaw the Eleusinian Mysteries during festival times was not present at the sanctuary all the time.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Notes: Some positions were always occupied by a specific gender.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– Yes

Notes: They were always Greek, or at least Greek-speaking.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– Yes

Notes: Some positions were held only by specific families. For example, the Hierophant (the most important priest at Eleusis) was always held by a member of the Eumolpidae. Most priests at the sanctuary came from either the Eumolpidae or the Kerykes.

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– Yes

Notes: Some offices were held for life upon appointment, such as that of the Hierophant, Dadouchos, the Priestess, the Iakchogogos, the Altar-Priest, the Keryx, etc.

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– Yes

Notes: The Anaktoron, a rectangular room within the Telesterion used as an inner sanctum, was accessible only to the Hierophant. Access to the various parts of the sanctuary, furthermore, was restricted based on level of initiation.

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: The Priestess was housed within the sanctuary.

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Notes: Greek priests/priestesses generally received little to no training as professional priesthoods generally did not exist. They were chosen by appointment, election, or random selection (like jury duty).

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– No

Notes: The epigraphic accounts for the finances at Eleusis list income from sacred land owned by the sanctuary but also offerings, donations, private benefaction, etc.

↳ Does this place lease out land:

– Yes

Notes: An inscription (I.Eleusis 176) concerns the lease of tenement houses.

↳ Does this place lease out tools:

– Field doesn't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Yes

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Yes

Notes: The Homeric Hymn to Demeter (composed orally late 7th/early 6th c. BC, written later), which contains the foundation myth of the sanctuary at Eleusis, is not a sacred text in the same sense as the Torah or the Qur'an but was sung/performed musically as a prayer.

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they written at this place:

– No

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

↳ Is there a story associated with the origin and/or construction of this place:

– Yes

↳ Are there religious specialists in charge of interpreting the scriptures:

– No

↳ Are the scriptures part of the building/place:

– No